

considerare l'accostamento tra i due autori quanto meno arrischiato. A metterli a confronto contribuisce la forma della tragedia di particolare successo al tempo di Tolomeo Filadelfo e di quella Pléiade di cui era membro un Licofrone, autore dell'*Alessandra*, secondo la cronologia di Hurst, e il desiderio di entrambi di fare luce sulla propria cultura, quella del *Pentateuco* per Ezechiele e l'ellenismo per Licofrone.

Gli echi della poesia alessandrina che, come è noto, percorrono la poesia latina dai *poetae novi* in poi sono messi in rilievo da Hurst principalmente nelle *Metamorfosi* di Ovidio che ospitano tra l'altro l'enigma e il gioco etimologico.

La rassegna si chiude con la prestigiosa figura di Gregorio di Nazianzo negli scritti del quale è possibile ravvisare le tracce della cultura greca e i parametri dell'ellenismo come nella consacrazione di Gregorio alla vita monastica da parte della madre in cui ricorrono ben riconoscibili stilemi alessandrini quali lo stretto sentiero e la porta sottile.

VALERIA GIGANTE LANZARA
vlanzara@gmail.com

JESSICA PICCININI, *Listening to the Past. New Perspectives in the Study of Ancient Soundscape. A Survey*

*A chi mi ha indicato la strada
per aver nuovi occhi.*

1. Ancient history and sound(scape) studies

Soundscape studies, a subfield of sound studies, is a multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, and transdisciplinary¹ area of research spanning a broad spectrum of the 'new humanities' – the overarching term for several subjects from the arts and sciences concerned with the study of man.² In the

¹ The terms 'multidisciplinary', 'interdisciplinary', and 'transdisciplinary' are increasingly employed in the humanities, but are often ambiguously defined and interchangeably used. In the interest of clarity, briefly the most recent definitions: 'multidisciplinarity' draws on knowledge from different disciplines, but within the boundaries of those fields; 'interdisciplinarity' examines, synthesizes, and harmonizes links between disciplines into a coordinated and coherent whole; 'transdisciplinarity', then, integrates the natural, social and health sciences in a humanities context, and in so doing transcends each of their traditional boundaries (CHOI – PAK 2006, p. 359).

² GOTTSCHALL 2008, pp. 1-87.

last decades several different fields of research have contributed to the debate, including archaeology, acoustics, history of art, linguistics, religious studies, anthropology, ethnomusicology, cognitive science, philosophy, history, cultural studies, and literature, as well as a few STEM disciplines.³ Each subject, with its own different questions, issues, and methodology converges in the effort to investigate the various and complex ways in which ancient people perceived and related to sounds, and more generally to the phonosphere. Sound studies also explores the ideas, motivations, and assumptions shaping these perceptions and relationships as well as their social, religious, and political effects and implications.

In the wake of this wide interest, classical studies has recently witnessed an upsurge in sound-related workshops, conferences, and publications, including several monographs, edited volumes, and articles; some of the most recent contributions – though with no claim to thoroughness – are the subject of this contribution. Although not all the publications reviewed deal explicitly with the larger, interdisciplinary debate, they all reflect an increased awareness in classical scholarship of the centrality of sound and soundscape in ancient evidence and contexts.

The milestone in this field is a work dating back almost fifty years. In 1977 the Canadian composer Raymond Murray Schafer, within the international research project ‘The World Soundscape’ held at Simon Fraser University, published a book entitled *The Soundscape. Our Sonic Environment and the Tuning of the World*, drawing attention to the concept of acoustic ecology, which he called ‘soundscape’, and through which he stressed the relationship between men and the acoustic environment. More specifically, his focus was on the perceptual construction of the acoustic environment of a place as perceived and interpreted by a human being.⁴ His observations,

³ Examples of collaboration between humanities and STEM disciplines are the recent works on archaeo-musicology and acoustic archaeology, often with the help of specific software, soundscape apps, and digital audio technologies (WATSON – KEATING 1999; LAWSON – SCARRE 2006; HELMER – CHICOINE 2013; TILL 2014; BELLIA – BUNDRICK 2018; MATTERN 2019; POWER 2019, p. 15; LYNCH – ROCCONI 2020; BELLIA 2021a). Sometimes computer modeling was used to reconstruct the acoustics of sites that only partially remain, as in the case of Stonehenge, or that no longer exist (TAKESHI – LAWRENCE COBEN 2006; TILL 2010, 2011 and 2014, p. 294; HOLTER *et alii* 2019, pp. 44-46; ALETTA – KANG 2020; PERROT 2020, p. 89; e.g., <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iiGzNGLnYJ4>).

⁴ The concept of soundscape was first introduced by SOUTHWORTH 1969, but widely used thanks to Raymond Murray Schafer (MURRAY SCHAFER 1977), and criticized by Timothy Ingold (INGOLD 2007 and 2011, pp. 136-138). Full critical discussion in HOWES 2015, VINCENT 2015 and ZEROUALI 2015. The word ‘soundscape’ (‘paysage sonore’ in French-speaking studies) has since become conventional to describe the acoustic environment perceived by humans in context. The acoustic environment

mostly concerning modern times, paved the way for the studies by Serres,⁵ Pettman,⁶ and Ihde,⁷ which offered theoretical discussions on the interaction between human beings and the natural and social environment through the medium of sounds and prompted a change of perspective in the study of the ancient world.

These inquiries connecting sound and landscape studies were greatly influenced by so-called phenomenological theory, which emphasizes the experiential and lived aspects of a particular construct at the time it occurs. According to this theory, which originated in the late 1960s and has proliferated in the humanities since the beginning of the twenty-first century, sound perception plays an integral role in shaping and constructing a spatial situation, as it happens, for instance in public spaces where functional sounds inform or warn of certain events, e.g., car horns and bells, or indicate the results of certain actions, e.g., the high-pitched beep emitted when a ticket is validated with an electronic punching machine.⁸ Michel Serres, in particular, focused on the interaction between sound, space, and the senses, according to which human beings are naturally disposed to be attuned to their surroundings.⁹ In fact, as sensoriality shapes, organizes, and gives meaning to social life, and, perhaps more importantly, activates and evokes affectivity, sound (as well as the other senses) enables human beings not only to produce social and material effects, but also to be affected, to be 'touched', and to be 'moved'. Dominic Pettman offered a series of inspiring lessons on 'how to listen to the world', included, but not limited to, its 'ecological voice', to which he assigned the Latin name of *vox mundi*.¹⁰ According to him, spaces are physi-

consists of natural sounds, including animal vocalization, biophony (i.e., the ambient sounds of the natural environment), geophony (i.e., the sounds of weather and other natural elements), and anthropophony (i.e., the environmental sounds created by men). Recently, on the definition of acoustic/sonic environment (i.e., the sound from all the sources that could be heard by someone in a space) and soundscape (the perceptual construction and interpretation of the acoustic/sonic environment) see LEX BROWN *et alii* 2016, pp. 1-2, 5-6.

⁵ SERRES 1985, p. 119.

⁶ PETTMANN 2017.

⁷ IHDE 2007².

⁸ HOLTER *et alii* 2019, pp. 44-46. Sound can also be regarded as the mediator of what Barry Blesser and Linda Ruth Salter have named 'aural architecture', the architecture of a space as perceived through focusing on the interactions between sound sources and spatial elements. Sound is therefore a dimension in which we experience space – its unique shape and scale – that gives form and meaning to all sonic events that occur within a given architecture (BLESSER – SALTER 2007, pp. 1-11).

⁹ SERRES 1985, p. 119; see also BARRETT 1994, p. 12; HAMILAKIS 2013, p. 124.

¹⁰ PETTMAN 2017, pp. 65-77. See also TILL 2014, p. 296.

cal locations, but a consciousness of sound, the act of listening to a space operated by human beings, begins to turn it into a place: sounds help with orienting men in the wider environment as voices, and sounds – and I would add silences – relate inevitably with the subjects recognizing them.

An interesting and fruitful example of enquiry exploiting the theoretical framework outlined above is Corbin's monograph on the *paysage sonore* of the 19th-century French countryside; since, as he argues, sounds are often referring to, or caused by, someone or something, they relate indissolubly to human activity as performed or interpreted by human beings. In this respect, the environment in which these sounds were produced is always a social more than a physical space as it reflects the interrelation between sound and people.¹¹

Don Ihde's work is particularly relevant since it also looks closely at the ancient world.¹² In his seminal study of the phenomenology of sound Ihde pointed out that modern scholarship tends to examine classical antiquity predominantly in visual terms,¹³ both because of the plethora of objects and images found and exhibited in archaeological sites, stored in museum collections, and exploited in modern reconstructions, and because of the primary role played by vision in Greek and Roman civilizations.¹⁴ This strong ocular bias, leading to the belief that, to a certain extent, sight is, epistemologically and empirically, the most privileged of the senses, as highlighted by Aristotle¹⁵ and implicitly accepted by 19th-century archaeology, gives the illusion that the eye can bridge the gap between the present and the past. Yet, monuments and artifacts offer neither direct nor unmediated access to the ancient world, as they always need to be interpreted and put in context.¹⁶ It is high time, therefore, as suggested by Ihde, for a «change of emphasis from the visual to the auditory dimension». This change in focus has the potential to give us the opportunity «to discover what may be missing» and to find forgotten material.¹⁷

Despite the novelty of these concepts and approaches, modern scholarship on the ancient world has focused mainly on other aspects of sound stud-

¹¹ CORBIN 1994; cf. also VINCENT 2015, pp. 21-28.

¹² IHDE 2007²; cf. also POWER 2019, p. 20.

¹³ IHDE 2007², pp. 5-15; see also MORALES 2004, pp. 8-9; MARSHALL 2010, pp. 49-50; SQUIRE 2016; POWER 2019, pp. 15-16.

¹⁴ SYNNOT 1991; RUTHERFORD 2004; HAMILAKIS 2013, p. 27; SQUIRE 2016, pp. 3-4; GHEDINI 2022.

¹⁵ Arist., *de anim.*, III 435a, 13-14 (cf. KIDD 2019, I). The Aristotelian hierarchy of the senses identified sight, hearing, and smell (in that order) as the human senses, whereas taste and touch were seen as the animal senses.

¹⁶ HAMILAKIS 2013, p. 40; SQUIRE 2016, pp. 8-30.

¹⁷ IHDE 2007², p. 13.

ies, following more traditional lines of research. Scholarly interest has generally been devoted to two, mutually dependent, areas of research: orality / aurality in ancient literature¹⁸ and ancient music, and related issues, such as the study of surviving musical notation treatises and musical instruments.¹⁹ The attention paid to both lines of research is not striking, considering that the first verses of western literature are imbued with sounds,²⁰ that Greek culture was fundamentally reliant on orality²¹ and aurality,²² and that music, along with dance, was considered a prominent art accompanying various fundamental events in the ancient world, especially in relation to religious activities.²³ Always present in war, marriages, funerals, rituals, dance, dramatic performances, etc., music was a social phenomenon, playing an integral part in ancient lives²⁴ as it could entertain, represent emotions, deliver messages, accompany, connect, guide, enhance, heal, and valorize any facet of life of a single individual and of a group.²⁵ Not only single performances, but also the specific spaces, contexts, and occasions, in which a musical event was framed, have been examined so to read and appraise their social, anthropological, cultural, and religious meanings.²⁶

In close connection with the aforementioned lines of research is the scholarly interest on the voice, mainly as an expression of the *logos* and me-

¹⁸ See, for instance, Brill's series on *Orality and Literature in the Ancient World* published in the *Mnemosyne Supplements*.

¹⁹ GENTILI – PRETAGOSTINI 1988; WEST 1992; BELLIA 2020. On ancient musical treatises and modern scholarship Aristoxenus, fr. 124 Wehrli (= Athen. XIV 632 a), on Aristoxenus and music cf. VISCONTI 1999 and 2000; Pseudo-Plut., *De musica*; but also, Cleonides, Nicomachus, Ptolemy, etc.; on Greek musical education COMOTTI 1991, p. 60; PAGLIARA 1996; ROCCONI 2004; CASTALDO *et alii* 2009; PELOSI 2014; PER-NIGOTTI 2014.

²⁰ SERRES 1985, p. 119; HOLTER *et alii* 2019, p. 44.

²¹ HAVELOCK 1982; ONG 1982; SVENBRO 1988; THOMAS 1991 and 1992; RISPOLI 1995, pp. 10-11.

²² According to the definition of COLEMAN (1996, pp. 27-33; 2007, p. 68) aurality is «the shared hearing of written texts» and combines aspects of both orality and literacy.

²³ GENTILI – PRETAGOSTINI 1988; WEST 1992; BELLIA 2020.

²⁴ BUKLEY 1994, p. 509; RISPOLI 1995, p. 22; FRITH 1996, p. 237; MELINI 2007, p. 10; BOTH 2009, p. 3; CASTALDO 2012, pp. 6-7; TILL 2014, p. 293. Many works also deal with the representations of sounds in visual arts and the material evidence as sound scenes are widely depicted on pots, in mosaics, and in sculpture, as well as in paintings and in sculptural representations (cf. BELLIA 2008, 2009, 2012; and the essays on iconography in BELLIA 2014).

²⁵ MERIANI 2003, p. 6; MELINI 2007, pp. 31-32.

²⁶ LEFEBVRE 1991, p. 117; INGOLD 2011, p. 136; CASTALDO 2012, p. 6; HAMILAKIS 2013, p. 11; MCINERNEY – SLUITER 2016; HAWES 2017, p. 5; BIRDSALL 2019, p. 210.

dium through which human beings communicate. The first comprehensive analysis of all ancient vocal manifestations, with a special focus on the Latin literary sources, is that of Maurizio Bettini (*Voci. Antropologia sonora del mondo antico*, Roma 2008), who mainly examined the unintelligible (but full of meaning) sounds emitted by animals. He investigates the *fónosfera*, i.e., Italian, 'soundscape', but although he had in mind and among his bibliographical references Murray Schafer's work, his book only occasionally focuses on human sounds as well as the change of meaning of certain sounds through time and space. Nevertheless, Bettini's study can certainly be considered the first wide-ranging attempt to investigate soundscape in the classical world after Murray Schafer's paradigmatic shift in research.

More recently, Guy Lachenaud (*Les routes de la voix. L'antiquité grecque et le mystère de la voix*, Paris 2013) investigated the use of the voice in ancient Greece, going through all the ancient literary evidence treating its sonic features such as vocal intensity, timbre, pitch, and musicality. The concept of soundscape in Lachenaud finds very little space as the author remained more tied to a traditional approach, which conceived of the human voice as a musical instrument. Even in this case, cultural and social aspects related to the voice in antiquity are left aside, apart from a limited, but interesting, section on the use of the voice in oratory and ritual moaning.²⁷ Equally thought-provoking are Lachenaud's observations on silence,²⁸ in line with the research carried out by Silvia Montiglio (*Silence in the Land of Logos*, Princeton 2010), whose monograph focused on the functions and meanings of silence as attested in ancient Greek poetry, tragedy, and oratory. Although silence, i.e., the lack of sound, should be considered as contributing to create a soundscape, no reference to Murray Schafer's theoretical framework is given in her work.

However interesting as they may be, these investigations, which explore how Greeks and Romans encountered music and voice and their absence in everyday life, almost never take into account the environment in which they were produced, experienced, and interpreted in the ancient world, nor do they review the change of significance attributed to sounds in the course of time and shifting contexts. Moreover, these investigations, apart from Bettini's in which ample space is given to animal sounds, examine only a few aspects, not considering that ancient sound is not necessarily and always

²⁷ LACHENAUD 2013, pp. 121-133.

²⁸ *Ibid.*, pp. 65-83; followed by CRIPPA 2015. On the value of silence, see CAGE 1961; on silence as element marking geographic space/place HOGG 2019, part. p. 166, p. 175; on the communicative character and the typologies of silence cf. JAKOBSON 1960; VALESIO 1986, pp. 374-386; TERRACINI 1988; CAPRETTINI 1989; LAURETANO 1989. On silence in classical literature, MONTIGLIO 2000, pp. 9-45; ANGELI BERNARDINI 2015; CELENTANO – NOËL 2020; PAPADODIMA 2020; ZANELLA 2022, pp. 28-58.

limited to human utterances and music, i.e., the intentional product of organized tones and silence.²⁹

Voices, sounds, noises, and silences in the ancient world could have (had) multiple meanings according to the context, time, perception, and interpretation of the listener(s). They neither had nor have univocal significance as they forge and characterize situations and places. Since human beings assign value and significance to sound and its absence, it is interesting to look at how ancient sources recorded, rearticulated, and interpreted them according to context, situation, and contemporary cultural models. For example, the cries of some animals might be of good or bad omen, announce good or bad seasons, evoke memories, move people's senses and emotions, and strike fear.³⁰ A work which explores the interpretation of sound as a social phenomenon, is the edited volume by Maria Teresa Schettino and Sylvie Pittia (*Les sons du pouvoir dans les mondes anciens*, Besançon 2012). They collected essays illustrating how in antiquity noises and voices, especially in public spaces, could have been exploited and perceived as instruments of power. Particularly interesting is the article by Emmanuèle Caire ('*Le bruit des assemblées: Athènes, Sparte, Tarante*', pp. 71-95), in which the author investigates the different perceptions and the social dimension of noise in the assemblies of Athens, Sparta, and Taras: the literary evidence, mainly Aristophanes, projects a negative image of the noises of the democracy, which mirrors the excesses of the symposia; on the contrary, roar of the crowd in Sparta and its colony has a more positive connotation as it reflects the aristocratic power, consensus, and rule. This rich collection of contributions, most of which are devoted to Roman contexts, demonstrates the potential of an investigation which can be applied to any ancient civilization, as is also demonstrated by the second conference on the theme organized in Strasbourg a few years later by Antonio Gonzales and Maria Teresa Schettino. The publication of the proceedings (*Les sons du pouvoir des autres. Actes du troisième colloque SoPHiA, Strasbourg, 27-28 mars 2014*, Besançon 2017), more forcefully than the volume discussed immediately above, focuses on the importance of sound in public spaces as experienced and perceived by human beings. Once again, most of the contributions deal with aspects of Roman history, apart from that by Anne Jacquemin on the *espace sonore* de Delphi as outlined by ancient authors: Plutarch, in particular, stresses how human and animal sounds animated the sacred space of the sanctuary at times of public gatherings ('*Les sons des autres: une gêne pour Plutarque?*', pp. 53-65). In this case as well, no reference to Murray Schafer is given throughout the book leading one to wonder whether his work was taken for granted or intentionally ignored.

In this same timeframe, the edited volume by Jean Christophe Courtil and Régis Courtray (*Sons et audition dans l'Antiquité*, Toulouse 2015) rides

²⁹ TILL 2014, p. 294; BUTLER – NOOTER 2019, pp. 2-3, 8.

³⁰ BETTINI 2008, p. 21.

the wave of sound studies, giving the impression, however, that in considering the ancient acoustic environment modern scholars cannot go much beyond the reductive consideration that music and musicality were the main features of the ancient sonic environment. Most of the articles in this monographic issue of the journal «Pallas» deal with musical aspects, but one, by Adeline Gran-Clément, stands out as it concerns the *paysage sonore* of the Greek sanctuaries of Delos and Delphi as recorded in the Homeric Hymn to Apollo ('*Le paysage sonore des sanctuaires grecs. Délos et Delphes dans l'Hymne homérique à Apollon*', pp. 119-134). In a comprehensive analysis of all the sensory data in the hymn, not limiting the examination to the sound effects, the author points out the change of soundscape in Delos, from dissonance to harmony at the birth of Apollo, and in Delphi, where all the elements, i.e., sounds, lights, smells, etc., radiate after the foundation of the oracle.

The urgency to frame these 'late-onset' interests in *paysage sonore* might have been at the base of the edited volume of Sibylle Emerit, Sylvain Perrot, and Alexandre Vincent (*Le paysage sonore de l'Antiquité. Méthodologie, historiographie et perspectives*, Le Caire 2015). For the first time, the issue was tackled systematically through a diachronic and interdisciplinary perspective. The first methodological and theoretical part deals critically with Murray Schaffer's category of soundscape and its reception in modern scholarship, not limiting the investigation to the ancient world; the second gathers four brief but accurate contributions giving an overview of the ancient evidence dealing with the *paysage sonore* in ancient Egypt, Mesopotamia, ancient Greece, and Rome. Because of their thorough inspection of sources, they set the basis for any further investigation on the topic. In particular, Sylvain Perrot's contribution ('*Pour une archéologie des expériences sonores en Grèce antique*', pp. 175-208) considers different paths of research, such as the role and importance of sound in Greek religion, and takes stock of aspects already highlighted by previous scholarship, such as the study of the voice, the lexicon of sound, music, and musical instruments.

Voices, sounds, and silences are, thus, variously the focus of recent works, either as a single topic or in combination, and covering different chronological and geographical ranges, from prehistory to late antiquity, from ancient Greece to the Roman world, and topics, i.e., politics, religion, literature, philology, philosophy, etc. Most, if not all, of these works offer insights into ancient uses and conceptions of sounds in various contexts and occasions and highlight the potential of this line of enquiry, as does the recent volume edited by Shane Butler and Sarah Nooter (*Sound and the Ancient Senses*, London 2019). Being the final issue of an interesting series on senses in antiquity,³¹ the book examines the role of sound and hearing in

³¹ <https://www.routledge.com/The-Senses-in-Antiquity/book-series/SENSESANT>.

the Greek and Roman world. The articles, which explore sounds in different contexts, confirm the assumption that sound played an important role in antiquity, contributing to give a social and political connotation to the different contexts in which it was used. And above all, they draw attention to the plethora of evidence concerning ancient sounds, their role, and their significance as recorded by sources, linking ancient scholarship with the modern debate. The book is divided into three thematic sections, namely ancient soundscape, theories of sounds, and philology and sounds; the last two offer more traditional insights, by focusing on ancient authors and philosophers who dealt with the characterization of human and animal sound and music. More innovative and thought-provoking for the present discussion is the first part, in which the contributions examine sound in specific contexts. In particular, the article by Erika Holter, Susanne Muth, and Sebastian Schwesinger highlights the importance of sound in Late Republican public spaces; the authors also attempt a 3D simulation of the perception and an acoustic reconstruction of a selection of Cicero's orations in the Forum assembly. Equally interesting is Timothy Power's contribution on sounds in sacred spaces, emphasizing the multisensorial aspects of Greek religious festivals and rites loaded with natural sounds and music.

More recently the edited volume by Jill Gordon (*Hearing, Sound, and the Auditory in Ancient Greece*, Bloomington 2022) explores the topic of sound and hearing in ancient Greek literature. The fifteen contributions offer different interesting insights on the way in which ancient sources considered natural and human voices, sense perception, sounds, music, and silence as elements shaping the ancient world. Given that the authorities considered, apart from Sophocles' *Philoctetes*, are five philosophers of the archaic and classical periods, i.e., Heraclitus, Empedocles, Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, the book highlights that there is scope to extend the analysis to other ancient authors.

2. Soundscape and Greek sanctuaries

Among the various strands of research offering fertile ground for sound studies, ancient religion is one of the most promising.

Greek religion was strongly oriented towards activity rather than contemplation, outward displays of worship rather than inwardly felt devotion, and diverse ritual practices circumscribed by local cults rather than universal adherence to a unifying dogma.³² Sound and hearing made a contribution to the holistic experience of these activities as significant as those made by im-

³² PARKER 2011, part. pp. 124-223.

age and sight. Thus, it is not uncommon to find acknowledgements of the 'multisensory' nature of certain Greek festivals and rites in ancient sources: their heady mix of sight, sounds, smells, and textures.³³

In sacred spaces sound worked to structure and texture ritual observance, communication and memory, and to stimulate emotional states in worshippers, which might be functional in giving the impression of being closer to the god(s): it sacralized space and time, intensifying the sense of the divine; it generated symbolic meanings that linked the moment to a broader imagined space; it could echo the mythical past in the here-and-now, and sustain the continuum between previous and current ritual events. Background noises, natural sounds, divine and human voices contribute to define, give shape and meaning to specific places, especially religious contexts, according to Lidov's definition of *hierotopia*.³⁴

Ancient sanctuaries were populated by voices and sounds of human beings praying, consulting, singing, and performing dramas and rituals, animals to be sacrificed and exploited for prophecies, divine utterances, and natural phenomena, such as thunderings, rainstorms, and winds, which created a highly significant and multisensorial environment. Crowds visiting shrines were not only passive auditors, but also made noises and sounds: besides professional musicians and artists competing and performing in shrines, devotees, as single visitors or groups, made rituals, songs, prayers, crying, etc., as well as interacting with and talking to each other.

Festivals were certainly the most complex soundscapes in religious contexts, fully engaging the visitors' ears: besides musical performances of all kinds, utterances, acclamations, screams of athletes engaged in contests, many were the sounds registered by ancient sources referring to the noisy crowds, the sounds of sacrifice made by animals, tools, and worshippers, the piercing cry of women when the animal was killed, which Walter Burkert memorably called «life scream over death».³⁵ Likewise, *theoriai* and processions were animated by voices and sounds. Pausanias, for instance, tells of a college of female devotees of Dionysus, i.e., the Thyades, whose biannual *theoria* from Athens to Delphi followed a 'songline': the women sounded out their sacred journey through the landscape with choral songs and dances at traditional stopping points along the route. Processions and rites, more specifically, were ceremonies featuring sounds, noises, and silences and, as

³³ POWER 2019, pp. 16-20. Although sound created these effects in tandem with vision and the other senses to give meaning to places and events, it could also operate independently, in ways vision could not, and thus leave unique impressions on social experience. Unlike an image, either static or mobile, it could pervade space and reach individuals and groups with an equal immediacy.

³⁴ LIDOV 2006.

³⁵ BURKERT 1985, p. 56; cf. also POWER 2019, pp. 17-18.

modern scholarship has highlighted, they engaged with the full sensory spectrum; Eftychia Stavrianopoulou cogently defines sacred procession as «the babble of voices, movement, music, colours, smells, and visual impressions».³⁶ Joan Connelly paid welcome attention to processional acoustics in her discussion of the grand *pompe* that travelled the Sacred Way from Athens to Eleusis for the celebration of the Mysteries.³⁷ A further example of a ritual in which sound played an important role, as featured by cheers, screams, neighs, hoof pawing, etc., as the *pannychis*, i.e., the night torch-race on horseback, inaugurating the Bendideia in Attica.³⁸

Beside this noisy environment, ancient sources also registered the lack of sound and several moments of silence in association with solemn rites and prayers in sacred spaces. One of these, for instance is, *euphemia*, i.e., the ritual silence, which punctuated and heightened pleas as well as aiming to acquire the favour of the god(s).³⁹

Sonic practices in religious contexts have generally been treated by modern scholarship descriptively, as mere adjuncts to visual experience. Beside the few dedicated articles already mentioned above,⁴⁰ several edited volumes have recently dealt closely with these phenomena, investigating on the one hand, the relationship between sound and religion, and on the other, that between soundscape and Greek sanctuaries. The first two are the proceedings of a conference organized in Velletri in 2013 as a collaboration between the Museum of Religions 'Raffaale Pettazzoni' and 'Eikonikos – Laboratorio di iconografia e iconologia del mondo classico' of the Scuola di Specializzazione in Beni Archeologici of the University of Cagliari. Igor Baglioni edited the contributions of several scholars of different disciplines, mostly working on Mediterranean religions and reception studies, investigating various types of sonorous manifestations in ancient and modern rituals, prayers, and festivals (*Ascoltare gli Dei / Divos Audire. Costruzione e percezione della dimensione sonora nelle Religioni del Mediterraneo Antico*, I-II, Roma 2015). Through a diachronic perspective, the articles deal with evidence relating to sound in Egyptian and Near Eastern religions as well as with the theme of sonic production and perception in modern and contemporary visual production. The section referring to Greek, Roman, and Christian sources was published in a second volume by Romina Carboni and Marco Giuman

³⁶ STAVRIANOPOULOU 2015, p. 355. See also WEBSTER 2019.

³⁷ CONNELLY 2011, p. 320, 316-319; cf. also MYLONOPOULOS 2011, pp. 103-109.

³⁸ Cf. Plat., *Resp.* I 328a; on the rite PARKE 1977, pp. 149-152; PARKER 2005, p. 166 and p. 182; PICCININI 2017, pp. 138-140 and 146-150.

³⁹ MONTIGLIO 2000, pp. 9-45; GÖDDE 2003, pp. 24-46; CHANIOTIS 2006, pp. 227-228, 237; POWER 2019, p. 17.

⁴⁰ GRAN-CLÉMENT 2015 on Delos and Delphi, JACQUEMIN 2017 on Delphi, PERROT 2019 on Sparta.

(*Sonora. La dimensione acustica nel mondo mitico, magico e religioso dell'antichità classica*, Perugia 2013). Most articles deal with the representations of sound in ancient archaeological and art historical evidence (i.e., music in the cult of Demetra in Sicily, musical instruments in Sicilian cults, sound in Mithraic rites), in literary sources (Ovid, Aelian, and texts about bird divination and war dances), and, interestingly for the first time, in epigraphical evidence, as a contribution by Lyuba Radulova and Rita Sassu focuses on the few inscriptions relating to the imperial cult from Nikopolis ad Histrum attesting the presence of an association of *hymnodoi philosebastoi*, engaged in performing hymns honoring the emperor.

Another volume, by Erika Angliker and Angela Bellia (*Soundscape and Landscape at Panhellenic Greek Sanctuaries*, Pisa-Roma 2021), deals more cogently with the relationship between soundscape and sacred landscape, with particular attention to ancient Greek sanctuaries.⁴¹ Five case studies are treated in relation to specific topics, focusing mainly on musical aspects. They concern the panhellenic sanctuary of Olympia, the Heraia in Magna Graecia, and some of the choral performances in Sparta; a further article treats the soundscape at Dodona, focusing on the gong, i.e., the peculiar *anathema* of the Corcyraens as recorded by ancient sources, and another examines, also from a geophysical perspective, the possible reconstructed sound characteristics of the sanctuary of Zeus on Mount Lykaio in Arcadia. None of them, except, very briefly, that on Dodona, examines in detail the literary and archaeological evidence concerning the phonosphere of a shrine.

Although quite different in scope, content, and outlook, these works on ancient sound have undoubtedly contributed to extend our knowledge of Greek and Roman religion, improving our understanding of the symbolic transactions underlying various seemingly disparate religious practices, including sacrifice, divination, and magic. Yet, a comprehensive study of the manifold roles and functions of sounds and soundscape of Greek sanctuaries, even limited to specific religious contexts, as attested in literary, archaeological, and epigraphical sources, is still lacking.

3. Concluding remarks and prospects

Jacques Derrida famously argued that the voice in the Western metaphysical tradition is more than a means of communicating, as it is posited as a source of self or identity.⁴² By the same line of reasoning, we could de-

⁴¹ On the sound dimension of Dodona, especially in relation to the gong of the Corcyreans, see CHAPINAL HERAS 2016; ANGLIKER 2021b; PICCININI 2022a and 2022b.

⁴² DERRIDA 2016⁴, p. 12. Cf. SAMPSON 2019, p. 124.

fine sound, noise, and silence as the elements exploited by human beings to feature a place and a context.⁴³ There are places where sound is not only expected, but also required to enact their specific functions: the marketplace, the assembly, the theatre, etc.

Greek landscapes have been studied in various ways, when modern scholarship became aware of the concept of 'space' as a means of analysis, showing both how places become imbued with meanings, and how they are represented, projected, and experienced; mythical accounts in literary sources, for instance, have been examined in relation to precise topographies, as stories might acquire particular significance and sense if located on mountains, islands, caves, and the sea,⁴⁴ but almost never in relation to their sonic quality.⁴⁵

We should not necessarily subscribe to Catullus' words (*quod vides perisse perditum ducas*)⁴⁶ and account 'as lost what we see is lost' since ancient literary and epigraphic evidence allows us to retrieve ancient sounds, to reconstruct the sonority of sacred landscapes, which are only seemingly mute, and to animate the scenario.⁴⁷ Through their analysis it is possible not only to represent the past as a picture might do, but also to evoke the quality of a lost context, to reignite its affective power as well as to ascertain changes of perception and significance of a single event and/or an environment.⁴⁸ The evocative power of the written language permits the awakening of the 'dead' medium and to recreate sensations, scenarios, frames, movements, and situations which are only apparently lost.⁴⁹

⁴³ According to Murray Schafer, soundscape is featured by keynote sounds, signals, and soundmarks: the keynote sounds of a landscape are those created by its geography and climate: water, wind, forests, plains, birds, insects, and animals; signals are foreground sounds and are listened to consciously; soundmarks refer to a community sound, which is unique or possesses qualities making it specially regarded or noticed by the people in that community (MURRAY SCHAFER 1977, pp. 8-10).

⁴⁴ DOUGHERTY 1993; BUXTON 1994, pp. 80-113; MACSWEENEY 2013; TILL 2014, p. 296; MACSWEENEY 2015; HAWES 2017, p. 4.

⁴⁵ Exceptions in this sense are the analysis of ancient performative contexts, but in this case, music and not sound, in the broad sense, is taken into account: KOWALZIG 2007; KÄPPEL 2015; HAWES 2017, p. 4; specifically on Attic festivals LIVERI 2021; on Magna Graecia's Heraia BELLIA 2021b.

⁴⁶ Cat. VIII 2.

⁴⁷ WATSON 2001, p. 180; BETTINI 2008, pp. 16-19, 22, 30. As for the epigraphic evidence, interesting insights come from the use of divine epiclesis, which can contribute to shed light on the nature of gods (e.g., SEG 29, 1772-1773: Selene Epekoos; SEG 39, 911: mooing Athena; SEG 42, 1812: Ζεὺς Βροντῶν).

⁴⁸ HAMILAKIS 2013, p. 10; BIJSTERVELD 2016, p. 100; BULL 2020, p. XXI.

⁴⁹ HAMILAKIS 2013, pp. 13, 201.

The general acoustic environment of a society can be read as an indicator of the social conditions which produce it and may tell us much about the trends and evolution of a society.⁵⁰ Only a total appreciation of the acoustic environment, perceived, conceived, and produced by people and nature,⁵¹ can give us the opportunity to assess and appreciate the orchestration of the world and the interaction between humans and soundscape over time.⁵²

This approach, which can be applied fruitfully to ancient sacred landscapes as glimpsed in this brief overview, is in line with recent scholarly attention to the interaction between sound, the hearers, and cultural spaces.⁵³ Previous phenomenological approaches,⁵⁴ especially those linked to landscape studies, have paved the way toward investigations that attempt to understand how materiality and human sensory and sensuous action and experience interact.⁵⁵ Yet perception can only meaningfully be studied in social contexts – that is, in an environment in which senses ‘mingle’ with the world.⁵⁶ In other words, perception does not simply go on in the head, but might have social, cultural, and political meanings. The study of ancient soundscape may offer a ground for innovative interpretations of a world of things rendered in their acoustic forms, to which human beings gave significance and by which they were affected.

Thus, the time seems ripe to set aside Aristotle’s privileged assessment of sight⁵⁷ and to bring to the foreground Plato’s words, who, through the mouth of Glaucon, affirms that we should «prefer the ears to the minds»,⁵⁸ since the most effective way to reach the soul and so influence mood and character is through hearing.⁵⁹

JESSICA PICCININI

jessica.piccinini@unimc.it

⁵⁰ MURRAY SCHAFER 1977, p. 7.

⁵¹ PERROT 2020, p. 89.

⁵² MURRAY SCHAFER 1977, p. 4.

⁵³ WATSON – KEATING 1999; WATSON 2001; BLESSER – SALTER 2007; MARSHALL 2010, p. 53.

⁵⁴ See *infra*.

⁵⁵ FELDMAN 1994, p. 104; TILLEY 1994 and 2004; BRÜCK 2005; HOWES 2005, p. 7; JOHNSON 2012; HAMILAKIS 2013, pp. 8-9; EDENSOR 2019, p. 160; HOLTER *et alii* 2019, p. 44.

⁵⁶ SERRES 1985; HOWES 2019, p. 31.

⁵⁷ Cf. n. 15.

⁵⁸ Plat., *Resp.* VII 531b.

⁵⁹ Plat., *Resp.* III 411a-c. Cf. recently the works of HASKELL 2014, 2018 and 2023.

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La disciplina archeologica non è nuova nel suo impiego al servirsi di strumenti, ritenuti ermeneutici, originatisi e utilizzati in discipline del tutto differenti, generalmente applicate a fenomeni moderni o addirittura contemporanei. Sembra questo il caso di quanto si vuole qui discutere. Si tratta degli atti di un convegno internazionale, celebratosi a Roma presso la Villa Lante, sede dell'*Institutum Romanum Finlandiae*, in collaborazione con l'Università IUAV di Venezia, nel maggio 2022, editi in un bel volume, riccamente illustrato.

«Il tema della relazione uomo-ambiente nel mondo antico, ossia, più precisamente, i modi della convivenza urbana con la natura nell'epoca imperiale romana, è attualmente il fulcro delle ricerche dell'*Institutum Romanum Finlandiae*»: così nella prefazione Ria Berg, direttore di questo, motiva l'organizzazione del convegno, e della successiva, tempestiva pubblicazione degli atti, situandola all'interno di una più ampia attività di ricerca. Finora ai “modi della convivenza urbana con la natura nell'epoca imperiale romana” chi scrive aveva associato le riflessioni di Paul Zanker a proposito delle *domus* costruite a cavallo delle mura di Pompei, aperte alla visione delle campagne circostanti la città. E, nei meandri della memoria, quanto ne scrive Plinio il Giovane a Domizio Apollinare a proposito della sua villa in Toscana. In questa il *cubiculum* diurno «piacevolmente ombreggiato dal vicino platano» era decorato con «ambientazioni di giardino... affrescate con vegetazione e uccelli (Plin., *Ep.* 5, 6, 22-23)». ¹ Così che non sembrava si avessero ansie psicologiche di età romana collegate al rapporto con la natura: quanto piuttosto le si riteneva rivolte a situazioni di genere politico o bellico, con il conseguente ripetersi di lutti e di violenze. E a tal proposito tornavano alla

¹ A. ANGISSOLA, *Intimità a Pompei. Riservatezza, condivisione e prestigio negli ambienti ad alcova di Pompei*, Berlin-New York, de Gruyter 2010, p. 50.